

Integrated clinical and wastewater genomics identify SARS-CoV-2 mutations from asymptomatic infections and hospitalization across the Omicron constellation

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Abstract

Wastewater (WW) genomics can track SARS-CoV-2 circulation beyond clinical testing, but its ability to reflect clinical diversity and capture severity-linked mutations remains incompletely defined. We compared mutations and lineages from 845 clinical and 22 wastewater sequences during the Omicron wave in two settings: the metropolitan area and a hospital from the city. Additionally, we investigated the presence of clinically relevant mutations in WW, by looking for mutations associated to hospitalization at three levels: regional, national and supranational level in 39,099 SARS-CoV-2 sequences.

We found partial overlap in lineage composition between WW and clinical samples, with higher overlap at the metropolitan (50%), than at the hospital level (30%). Conversely, we found a slightly higher overlap of individual mutations between WW and clinical samples at the hospital level (20%) than at the metropolitan area (16%), but shared mutations in both datasets were enriched in the Spike gene.

Clade composition did not differ between 216 hospitalised and 528 non-hospitalised cases at regional level. Using GWAS and Hierarchical Lasso analysis, we detected mutations associated with hospitalization status in three different datasets: regional, national and worldwide, with little overlap between them. Although few variants replicated across cohorts, the overlap between the Spain and global analyses was

40 statistically enriched and centred on RBD substitutions (D405N, K417N, R408S).
41 Multiple integration of genomic association results prioritised 34/191 wastewater
42 mutations (16 in Spike), including one mutation only detected in wastewater missed by
43 routine clinical surveillance. Wastewater sequencing tracked dominant Omicron waves
44 but performance varied by catchment; integrating clinical association results with
45 interaction network modelling helped prioritise and interpret wastewater-detected
46 mutations.

47 Keywords

48 Wastewater, SARS-CoV-2, GWAS, Omicron, hospitalisation.

49 Introduction

50 In 2026, SARS-CoV-2 remains a globally circulating respiratory pathogen whose
51 ongoing evolution under a shifting population-immunity landscape continues to reshape
52 transmissibility and immune escape¹, with episodic surges that can still translate into
53 substantial healthcare burden². Genomic surveillance therefore remains a cornerstone
54 of COVID-19 risk assessment and response, enabling early detection and tracking of
55 emerging variants, rapid characterisation of defining mutations, and reconstruction of
56 transmission dynamics across spatial scales; international guidance continues to
57 recommend maintaining and strengthening these surveillance systems as part of
58 broader preparedness for respiratory threats³. However, the utility of any genomic
59 surveillance system is ultimately constrained by the representativeness and
60 completeness of the sampled infections: uneven sequencing coverage, reporting
61 delays, and structural disparities can leave a substantial fraction of infections,
62 particularly mild or asymptomatic cases, undiagnosed or unsequenced, limiting
63 inference on circulating diversity and on genotype–phenotype links⁴.

64 The Omicron constellation underscored why continuous, fine-scale monitoring
65 remained necessary even in highly immunised populations. Across multiple settings,
66 Omicron infection was associated with a substantially lower risk of hospitalisation and
67 death than Delta, although the magnitude of risk reduction varied by age and immune
68 background and, during high-incidence waves, still translated into large absolute
69 numbers of hospital admissions. At the same time, Omicron diversified rapidly,
70 producing successive waves of sublineages with extensive Spike evolution and immune
71 evasion; recombinant XBB lineages in particular showed near-complete escape from
72 neutralising antibodies in several experimental settings, highlighting how quickly
73 antigenic change accumulated within Omicron's genetic space^{5,6}. Subsequently,
74 phylogenetically distinct Omicron-descended lineages such as BA.2.86 and its
75 descendants were characterised as antigenically divergent and capable of efficient
76 spread, while exhibiting attenuated intrinsic pathogenicity in animal models compared
77 with some earlier variants, reinforcing the need to track both virological properties and
78 clinical correlates of emerging lineages^{7,8}.

79 Clinical genomic surveillance, built around sequencing respiratory samples from
80 diagnosed patients, has delivered major insights into SARS-CoV-2 evolution and
81 spread⁹⁻¹¹. Yet clinical sampling is inherently shaped by testing behaviour, health-
82 seeking patterns, and healthcare access, and is often enriched for symptomatic
83 infections and for individuals more likely to present for care¹². These biases can be
84 magnified as routine testing declines and sequencing strategies become increasingly
85 targeted, potentially reducing sensitivity for early detection of new variants and for
86 capturing the mutational diversity circulating in mild or asymptomatic infections^{11,13}. In
87 addition, linking viral genotypes to clinically meaningful endpoints such as
88 hospitalisation remains challenging because outcome risk is strongly driven by host
89 factors (for example age and comorbidity) and by immunity from vaccination or prior
90 infection, while viral effects can be confounded by lineage background and
91 transmission context¹⁴.

92 Wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE) provides a complementary surveillance
93 framework that can partially overcome these limitations by sampling pooled community
94 excreta^{15,16}. Multiple early studies demonstrated that SARS-CoV-2 RNA is detectable in
95 sewage and can provide actionable early signals of community transmission. In the
96 Netherlands, SARS-CoV-2 RNA was detected in sewage during the early emergence of
97 COVID-19, including in samples collected before widespread recognition of local
98 transmission¹⁷⁻¹⁹. In the Valencian region, longitudinal wastewater testing similarly
99 indicated that viral RNA trends anticipated increases in declared clinical cases,
100 supporting WBE as a sensitive and cost-effective surveillance strategy^{20,21}. In a high-
101 resolution time series in Connecticut, wastewater measurements tracked community
102 infection dynamics and preceded clinical indicators such as hospital admissions,
103 highlighting WBE as an early warning tool at population scale^{15,19,22}. These observations
104 align with evidence that SARS-CoV-2 RNA can be detected in stool and that faecal
105 shedding may persist beyond respiratory detection in some individuals, implying that
106 wastewater integrates signals across stages of infection and recovery²³⁻²⁶.

107 Beyond quantification, wastewater sequencing has matured into a powerful approach
108 for variant and mutation surveillance in complex mixed samples^{27,28}. Genome
109 sequencing directly from sewage has been shown to recover regionally prevalent
110 SARS-CoV-2 genotypes and to identify additional genetic variants not yet observed in
111 local clinical sequencing efforts, indicating that wastewater can capture diversity
112 missed by patient-based sampling²⁹. High-throughput wastewater sequencing has
113 likewise revealed extensive single-nucleotide variation, including mutations that were
114 not present in global clinical datasets at the time of sampling, supporting the idea that
115 pooled wastewater can provide a broader snapshot of circulating diversity because
116 both symptomatic and asymptomatic infections contribute to sewage³⁰⁻³². More
117 recently, large-scale wastewater genomics has demonstrated the ability to detect
118 emerging variants earlier than clinical surveillance and to uncover cryptic transmission
119 patterns^{11,27}. A prominent example showed that wastewater sequencing detected
120 emerging variants of concern up to two weeks earlier and identified multiple instances
121 of variant spread not captured by clinical genomic surveillance. These results have

122 motivated formal guidance encouraging integration of environmental surveillance with
123 clinical systems to strengthen situational awareness and decision-making¹⁵.

124 Despite these advances, converting wastewater sequence data into clinically
125 interpretable signals is technically and analytically demanding. Wastewater RNA is often
126 fragmented and present at low concentrations, and sequencing reads represent
127 mixtures of multiple co-circulating lineages whose defining mutations co-occur on
128 distinct haplotypes. This complicates lineage deconvolution and mutational
129 interpretation, and motivates continuous methodological development and
130 benchmarking^{27,33,34}. Even when lineage prevalence can be estimated reliably, a key
131 open question for precision public health is how best to connect wastewater-detected
132 genetic signals to clinically meaningful outcomes, particularly during periods when
133 clinical case ascertainment is incomplete^{11,33}. Recent work has emphasised that
134 wastewater genomics can support epidemiological investigations even when clinical
135 samples are unavailable, and that shifts in mutation patterns in wastewater may provide
136 early signals of lineage transitions^{11,29}. However, fewer studies have explicitly addressed
137 whether wastewater can capture and prioritise mutations that are informative for
138 severity-related endpoints, such as hospitalisation risk¹⁵.

139 This gap is particularly relevant in the current Omicron era, where large-scale
140 transmission can coincide with fluctuating hospital burden, and where the mutational
141 landscape is shaped by strong immune selection and frequent convergent evolution in
142 spike³⁵. If wastewater could reliably detect mutations that are associated with severe
143 clinical outcomes, it could complement hospital-based surveillance by providing earlier
144 or more comprehensive coverage of severity-linked viral genetic changes, including
145 contributions from asymptomatic or under-ascertained infections that are not
146 represented in clinical sequencing datasets. Achieving this requires integrated study
147 designs that combine (i) catchment-matched wastewater sampling, (ii) well-annotated
148 clinical genomes spanning hospitalised and non-hospitalised infections, and (iii)
149 analytical frameworks that can reconcile univariate association signals with
150 multivariable, lineage-confounded mutational co-occurrence^{33,36}.

151 Here, we address these needs using a paired clinical and wastewater genomic
152 surveillance framework in Valencia, Spain, focusing on the Omicron constellation during
153 mid-2023 to mid-2024. Building on established evidence that wastewater RNA trends
154 can anticipate clinical indicators in multiple settings, including Valencia²¹, and on recent
155 demonstrations that wastewater sequencing can detect emerging variants earlier than
156 clinical sampling¹¹, we integrate two complementary catchments: a metropolitan
157 wastewater treatment plant serving a large urban area, and a hospital sewer collector
158 representing a healthcare-associated catchment. Using Nextclade and Pango-informed
159 lineage summaries and mutation-level analyses, we evaluate how well wastewater
160 reflects lineage diversity observed in clinical infections, quantify overlap and temporal
161 offsets between compartments, and examine the extent to which wastewater captures
162 mutations observed in hospitalised versus non-hospitalised cases. Finally, to connect
163 wastewater-detectable mutations to clinical severity, we combine univariate
164 hospitalisation association analyses with regularised multivariable interaction models to

165 prioritise candidate mutations and mutational modules that are both detectable in
166 wastewater and supported by independent severity-linked signals. By grounding
167 wastewater genomics in clinically annotated outcomes within a single, well-defined
168 geographic setting, this work aims to clarify when and how wastewater surveillance can
169 serve not only as an early warning system for circulation and variant replacement, but
170 also as a complementary window into severity-relevant viral genetic variation during
171 continued Omicron diversification²⁹.

172 Methods

173 Wastewater sample collection and RNA extraction

174 The dataset comprised 33 processed samples collected in Valencia, Spain, between
175 June 2023 and May 2024. Wastewater samples were obtained from two catchments:
176 (i) the sewer collector of Hospital General Universitario de Valencia (WW-Hospital) (n =
177 16) and (ii) the influent of the wastewater treatment plant (WW-Metroplitan) (n = 17). For
178 process validation, negative controls consisting of diethyl pyrocarbonate (DEPC)-
179 treated water were included alongside sample processing, and a positive control
180 consisted of RNA from an HGUV SARS-CoV-2-positive clinical specimen.

181 For each wastewater sample, 1 L of raw wastewater was collected and transported to
182 the Institute of Agrochemistry and Food Technology, CSIC (IATA-CSIC) under
183 refrigerated conditions ($5 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$). Viral concentration was performed following the
184 Spanish Ministry of Health protocol for SARS-CoV-2 detection in wastewater, as
185 previously described³⁷. Briefly, wastewater was concentrated by aluminium chloride
186 (AlCl_3) flocculation/precipitation followed by sequential centrifugation (20 min at 1,700–
187 1,800 \times g and 30 min at 1,900–2,000 \times g). Concentrates were recovered in a final
188 volume of 1–2 mL.

189 Viral RNA was extracted from the concentrated material and eluted in a final volume of
190 50 μL . Extracted RNA was transported to I2SysBio on dry ice and stored at -80°C until
191 downstream molecular processing.

192 Sequencing and bioinformatic analysis of Clinical and Wastewater 193 samples

194 Clinical specimens were confirmed as SARS-CoV-2 positive by reverse transcription
195 PCR (RT-PCR) in the corresponding clinical microbiology laboratories. Viral RNA was
196 reverse-transcribed into cDNA and amplified using the ARTIC Network tiled-amplicon
197 approach with the SARS-CoV-2 primer scheme version 5.2 (two multiplex PCR pools).
198 Amplicon pools were combined and used for library preparation. Most clinical samples
199 were sequenced using Illumina short-read technology. In addition, a subset of clinical
200 samples was sequenced using Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT). Nanopore
201 sequencing was performed on ONT devices using R9.4.1 and R10.4.1 flow cells following
202 the manufacturer's recommendations. Wastewater samples were processed

203 analogously for SARS-CoV-2 whole-genome amplification with the ARTIC v5.2 primer
204 scheme using Illumina short-read technology.

205 Illumina and Nanopore data were processed using the nf-core/viralrecon pipeline
206 (amplicon mode). Reads were analysed against the SARS-CoV-2 reference genome
207 (Wuhan-Hu-1, NC_045512.2). For Illumina data, the nf-core/viralrecon pipeline included
208 read QC (FastQC/MultiQC), adapter trimming and filtering (fastp), reference-based
209 alignment (Bowtie2) and BAM processing (SAMtools). ARTIC v5.2 primers were trimmed
210 using iVar trim with the corresponding BED file, duplicates were marked (Picard), and
211 depth/coverage profiles were computed (mosdepth). Variants were called with iVar in
212 amplicon mode and consensus genomes were generated with iVar consensus while
213 masking low-support positions; when enabled, variant summaries/annotation (bcftools,
214 SnpEff) and lineage/clade assignment (Pangolin, Nextclade) were also produced. For
215 wastewater samples, the same framework was used to estimate site-level mutation
216 frequencies from read evidence. For Nanopore data, viralrecon performed platform-
217 specific QC (pycoQC/NanoPlot), ARTIC amplicon length filtering (artic guppyplex), and
218 variant calling/consensus generation via the integrated ARTIC minion workflow,
219 producing FASTA/VCF outputs, BAMs, and coverage metrics (SAMtools, mosdepth),
220 with lineage assignment (Pangolin/Nextclade) and consolidated MultiQC reports. For
221 clinical samples, single nucleotide polymorphisms were called using a minimum read
222 depth of 20 \times , a minimum base quality of Q20, at least 4 supporting reads (minimum 2
223 on each strand), and a minimum SNP allele frequency of 5%. For wastewater samples,
224 the same criteria were applied, except that the minimum base quality threshold was
225 lowered to Q15 (minimum depth 20 \times).

226 Sampling framework for clinical outcomes and wastewater 227 comparisons

228 For catchment-matched comparisons between SARS-CoV-2 sequences from clinical
229 cases with documented outcomes and corresponding wastewater (WW) samples, two
230 datasets were defined: a metropolitan dataset linked to the WW-Metropolitan and a
231 hospital dataset linked to the Hospital General Universitario de Valencia (WW-Hospital)
232 sewer collector. For the metropolitan dataset, we compiled 1,933 clinical sequences
233 collected between 7 June 2023 and 29 August 2024, together with 17 WW samples
234 collected up to 31 January 2024 at an approximately biweekly frequency (Supplemental
235 Figure S1A). For the Hospital dataset, we compiled 449 clinical sequences collected
236 between 9 June 2023 and 26 August 2024, together with 15 WW samples from the
237 HGUV collector; sampling frequency was irregular overall, but increased during
238 January–February 2024 with intervals of 1–5 days (Supplemental Figure S1B).

239 For all sequenced samples, genome coverage was assessed across the full
240 SARS-CoV-2 genome, and only sequences meeting a minimum genome mapped across
241 the reference (coverage $\geq 50\%$) were retained for downstream comparative analyses
242 for both datasets (Supplemental Figure S2). To maximise temporal comparability
243 between clinical and WW surveillance and to minimise biases introduced by uneven WW
244 sampling and variable genome completeness, we restricted formal WW vs. clinical

245 comparisons to two predefined sampling windows with consistent sampling and
246 adequate coverage: 9 July 2023 to 8 December 2023 for the metropolitan dataset, and
247 29 December 2023 to 12 February 2024 for the Hospital dataset. The WW-Hospital
248 window coincided with increased sampling intensity around the Christmas 2023
249 epidemiological wave, including extended collection time at the hospital collector. In the
250 two datasets, the median timing difference between paired wastewater and clinical
251 sampling points was 10 days (wastewater sampled later than clinical) and 9 days
252 (clinical sampled later than wastewater), respectively.

253 Cohorts for hospitalisation association analysis

254 To construct the national and global cohorts used for hospitalisation-associated variant
255 analyses, we retrieved SARS-CoV-2 consensus genomes and accompanying metadata
256 from GISAID (data access date: 7 May 2025). We queried records with sample collection
257 dates between 7 June 2023 and 31 August 2024, yielding 87,052 sequences matching
258 the search criteria. Sequence quality was assessed with Nextclade v, and genomes
259 classified as “bad” were excluded. We then retained only records with a reported
260 hospitalisation status and manually curated key covariates used for adjustment,
261 including sex, age, and hospitalisation metadata, harmonising heterogeneous
262 submitter-provided annotations into standardised fields and removing entries that were
263 missing or internally inconsistent. Downstream genomic analyses were performed using
264 only the consensus FASTA sequences deposited in GISAID (. For the Spain-wide cohort
265 and Comunitat Valenciana cohort, we restricted it to sequences with sampling location
266 of interest, whereas the global cohort included sequences from all countries passing
267 the same filters. The resulting analytic datasets comprised the Comunitat Valenciana
268 cohort (n=4,848), Spain cohort (n = 10,052) and the global cohort (n = 39,099), both
269 with hospitalisation status and curated covariates available for association testing
270 (Figure 3).

271 Analysis of lineages across type of samples

272 Catchment-matched lineage comparisons were performed using two datasets from
273 Valencia, Spain: WW-TP and hospital sewer collector WW-Hosp. Lineages were
274 assigned from consensus genomes using Nextclade clades as the primary category,
275 with the corresponding Pango lineage reported in parentheses for interpretation.

276 To test whether lineage composition differed between hospitalised and non-
277 hospitalised cases, we constructed a contingency table of clade × outcome counts and
278 applied a Pearson χ^2 test of independence; effect size was summarised using Cramér's
279 V. To account for temporal confounding due to lineage turnover, we repeated this
280 comparison using a Cochran–Mantel–Haenszel-type stratified test with strata defined
281 by epidemiological week. Clade-set overlap between compartments (hospitalised, non-
282 hospitalised, and wastewater in WWTP; clinical and wastewater in WWTP-hosp) was
283 quantified using the Jaccard index computed from the set of clades observed at least
284 once in each compartment. To evaluate concordance of clade compositions between
285 wastewater and contemporaneous clinical sampling, each wastewater sampling date

286 was paired to clinical genomes collected within the corresponding comparison window,
287 and clade frequencies were converted to relative abundance vectors. For each paired
288 date we computed Jensen–Shannon divergence (JSD) and Bray–Curtis dissimilarity
289 between wastewater and clinical compositions, and summarised concordance by the
290 mean distance across the 11 paired dates. Statistical support for temporal matching was
291 assessed with a permutation test in which clinical composition vectors were randomly
292 assigned to wastewater dates (preserving the set of vectors) to generate a null
293 distribution for the mean distance. In addition, we quantified rank-level agreement
294 between wastewater and clinical clade frequencies using Spearman correlation,
295 computed over the paired relative abundances across all clade–date pairs. Finally, to
296 quantify timing differences in clade detection, we calculated for each clade observed
297 in both wastewater and clinical data the difference between its first detection date in
298 wastewater and in clinical surveillance (positive values indicate wastewater lagging
299 behind clinical); the median delay was tested against zero using a Wilcoxon signed-rank
300 test. All figures were generated using custom Python scripts (pandas/numpy) and
301 visualised with matplotlib.

302 Mutational analysis between datasets

303 Mutational profile comparisons between clinical outcomes and wastewater surveillance
304 were performed with custom Python scripts. Variant calls (nucleotide and amino acid
305 changes relative to reference) were restricted to callable positions (mask = 0) using the
306 study-wide calling thresholds, aggregated by dataset (metropolitan area WW-TP;
307 hospital collector WW-hosp) and group, and deduplicated by genomic coordinate (or
308 amino-acid position for protein-level analyses) so each site contributed once per
309 dataset × group. Overlap was visualised with Venn diagrams and quantified using the
310 Jaccard index. To test whether pairwise overlaps exceeded random expectation, we
311 used one-sided Fisher’s exact (hypergeometric) tests on 2×2 tables defined over the
312 dataset-specific mutation universe (union of sites observed across groups), reporting
313 OR and *P* values and applying Benjamini–Hochberg FDR where multiple comparisons
314 were performed. Differences in clinical–WW overlap between catchments were
315 assessed as Δ Jaccard with support evaluated by non-parametric bootstrap resampling
316 (recomputing mutation sets and Jaccard per resample). Mutations were mapped to
317 genes using the SARS-CoV-2 reference annotation to generate gene-level counts and
318 within-gene percentages, and enrichment of shared WW–clinical mutations in specific
319 genes (e.g., Spike) was tested with Fisher’s exact tests versus the rest of the genome
320 (BH-FDR). For Spike, amino-acid positions were assigned to canonical domains (NTD,
321 RBD, SD1, SD2, FP, HR1, CH, CD, HR2); we tested global domain-distribution differences
322 across groups with a χ^2 test, followed by one-sided Fisher tests for group–domain
323 enrichments with BH-FDR. Shared and group-specific Spike mutations were mapped
324 onto the Spike structure PDB:6VXX in PyMOL (mutations as spheres on a domain-
325 coloured surface; uncovered regions not rendered), and plots were generated with
326 pandas/numpy/matplotlib and exported as high-resolution outputs.

327 Mutations associated with hospitalisation

328 Associations between SARS-CoV-2 amino acid substitutions and clinical outcome were
329 analysed using custom R and Python scripts implementing a harmonised workflow
330 across three cohorts (Comunitat Valenciana, Spain-wide, and global with consensus
331 mutations calls). Recurrent amino acid substitutions were encoded as a binary
332 presence/absence matrix and tested against a binary phenotype (hospitalised vs
333 non-hospitalised), adjusting for age, sex, and location.

334 To account for population structure, a cohort-specific maximum-likelihood phylogeny
335 was inferred from the multiple sequence alignment with problematic regions masked
336 (https://github.com/W-L/ProblematicSites_SARS-CoV2) using IQ-TREE2³⁸ (GTR+F, --
337 polytomy, 1,000 ultrafast bootstraps, multithreading), and the resulting tree was
338 converted to a phylogeny-derived distance/structure term (via distree v1.0.0;
339 <https://github.com/PathoGenOmics-Lab/distree>) for downstream models.

340 In the Comunitat Valenciana cohort, each substitution was tested using covariate-
341 adjusted logistic regression with significance assessed by a likelihood-ratio test (LRT);
342 effect sizes were reported as $\log_2(\text{OR})$. In the Spain and global cohorts, single-variant
343 association was performed using pyseer³⁹ v1.3.11 in binary-trait GWAS mode, testing
344 each substitution while adjusting for age, sex, location, and the phylogeny-derived
345 structure correction. Within each cohort, multiple testing was controlled using
346 Bonferroni correction ($\alpha = 0.05/m$, where m is the number of tested substitutions), and
347 a suggestive threshold ($P = 1 \times 10^{-3}$) was used for visualization.

348 Cross-cohort consistency was quantified by testing enrichment of overlap among
349 Bonferroni-significant variants using Fisher's exact/hypergeometric tests, evaluating
350 directional concordance of replicated hits with a one-sided binomial test, assessing
351 effect heterogeneity with Cochran's Q, and measuring effect-size concordance using
352 Pearson correlation of $\log_2(\text{OR})$ with bootstrap 95% confidence intervals.

353 To capture multivariable and potentially non-additive relationships, we fitted regularised
354 interaction models with glinternet (hierarchical group-lasso) in the Spain and global
355 cohorts using amino acid substitutions and covariates as predictors; λ was selected by
356 cross-validation, and non-zero main effects and pairwise interactions were summarised
357 as interaction networks. The contribution of interactions was evaluated by Δ deviance
358 relative to a main-effects-only model, and robustness was assessed by bootstrap
359 stability selection (reporting node/edge selection frequencies; ≥ 0.8 considered stable);
360 inferred edges were interpreted as regularisation-selected statistical dependencies
361 rather than direct mechanistic interactions. Figures were produced with custom Python
362 scripts using pandas, numpy, and matplotlib (pyplot, TwoSlopeNorm,
363 LinearSegmentedColormap, FancyBboxPatch, Line2D), with interaction networks
364 extracted in R using glinternet.

365 Results

366 Lineage distribution partially overlaps between clinical and 367 wastewater samples

368 We assessed how well wastewater (WW) sequencing reflects lineage diversity
369 observed in clinical infections, and whether lineage composition differs between
370 hospitalised and non-hospitalised cases, using two catchment-matched datasets from
371 Valencia, Spain (Figure 1A). Lineages were summarised at the Nextclade clade level
372 (Pango lineage in parentheses) (Figure 1D–G). In both datasets, all detected clades
373 belonged to the Omicron constellation, with XBB-derived clades dominating in 2023 and
374 BA.2.86/JN.1 dominating in early 2024 (Figure 1F–G).

375 For the metropolitan dataset (9 July to 8 December 2023), we analysed 744 clinical
376 genomes (216 hospitalised and 528 non-hospitalised) and 11 unique WW samples
377 (Figure 1B). Clinical infections were dominated by 23F (EG.5.1) in both outcome groups
378 (32.9% in hospitalised and 32.2% in non-hospitalised). Consistent with this, lineage
379 composition did not differ between hospitalised and non-hospitalised cases in a global
380 contingency test ($\chi^2 = 8.764$, $p = 0.6437$; Cramér's $V \approx 0.11$) and remained non-
381 significant after adjustment by week (CMH-like $p = 0.6645$). Hospitalised and non-
382 hospitalised cases shared the same clinical clade set (12/12 shared; Figure Sx). Across
383 the 14 clades detected when considering clinical and WW together, WW recovered 9/14
384 (64.3%) and 7/14 clades were detected in all three compartments (hospitalised, non-
385 hospitalised, and WW), yielding partial clade-set overlap (Jaccard = 0.50; intersection
386 = 7, union = 14; Figure 1D). When comparing clade compositions across the 11 paired
387 WW–clinical same timepoints, we did not find significant concordance (mean JSD =
388 0.6131, $p = 0.2615$; mean Bray–Curtis = 0.9597, $p = 0.2438$) and rank correlation of clade
389 frequencies was low (Spearman $\rho = 0.110$, $p = 0.173$). So, clades that are more common
390 in clinical samples on a given date did not tend to be more common in wastewater on
391 the same date.

392 For the hospital dataset (29 December 2023 to 12 February 2024), we analysed 101
393 hospitalised clinical genomes and 11 unique WW samples (Figure 1C). Clinical infections
394 were dominated by 24A (JN.1) (89.1%), while WW frequently detected 23I (BA.2.86)
395 (10/11, 90.9%) and 24A (JN.1) (7/11, 63.6%) (Figure 1G). Across 10 distinct clades
396 detected across clinical and WW, 3/10 were shared (30.0%; Jaccard = 0.30;
397 intersection = 3, union = 10; Figure 1E). As in metropolitan area dataset, when comparing
398 clade compositions across the 11 paired WW–clinical at the same timepoint, we also did
399 not find significant concordance between groups (mean JSD = 0.84698, $p = 0.7401$;
400 mean Bray–Curtis = 0.97519, $p = 0.4053$; Spearman $\rho = 0.0968$, $p = 0.3145$).

401

402 **Figure 1. Sampling framework and SARS-CoV-2 lineage dynamics in matched clinical and**
 403 **wastewater datasets from the Valencia metropolitan area and Hospital General Universitario de**
 404 **Valencia (HGU).** (A) Geographic context and catchment definition. Left, location of Valencia
 405 Province within Spain and zoomed into the Valencia metropolitan area. Right, municipalities of
 406 residence for sequenced clinical cases are shown as circles scaled by the number of genomes
 407 (labels indicate counts), and sequencing hospitals are indicated by blue crosses (numbers next
 408 to each hospital indicate the number of genomes contributed). The Pinedo wastewater
 409 treatment plant (WWTP) sampling point is shown as a blue diamond, and municipalities correspond to areas
 410 draining to this WWTP. The hospital dataset refers exclusively to hospital clinical cases and
 411 wastewater collected from the hospital sewer collector. (B–C) Temporal distribution of
 412 sequenced samples (bars) and 7-day rolling mean (black line) for the metropolitan dataset linked
 413 to the Pinedo WWTP (B) and for the hospital dataset (C). (D–E) Venn diagrams summarising
 414 clades and Pango lineages detected in each dataset, showing shared and group-specific clades
 415 for the metropolitan dataset across wastewater, non-hospitalised and hospitalised groups (D),
 416 and for the hospital dataset between hospital wastewater and hospitalised clinical cases (E).
 417 Counts and percentages refer to the total number of distinct clades detected within each Venn

418 diagram. **(F–G)** Temporal variation in clade composition is shown as stacked area plots of relative
419 clade frequencies for each group in the metropolitan dataset (F) and in the hospital dataset.
420 Nextclade clades are annotated with the corresponding Pango lineages in parentheses; low-
421 frequency assignments are grouped as Other/Minor.

422 The difference in mutation repertoire between clinical and 423 wastewater is slightly higher at metropolitan than at hospital level

424 We next compared SARS-CoV-2 mutation profiles (nucleotide and amino-acid changes
425 relative to the reference) between clinical infections stratified by hospitalisation status
426 and matched wastewater (WW) samples in two catchments from Valencia (Figure 2). In
427 the Pinedo WWTP metropolitan dataset, we detected 1,006 mutations in non-
428 hospitalised clinical genomes, 546 in hospitalised genomes, and 191 in WW (Figure 2A).
429 Despite a large shared clinical core, WW recovered only a subset of the clinical
430 mutational space. Specifically, 300 mutation sites were shared across all three groups
431 (clinical and WW), and 464 sites were shared between hospitalised and non-
432 hospitalised cases only (Figure 2A). In contrast, WW shared relatively few mutations
433 exclusively with one clinical outcome group (18 sites with non-hospitalised and 4 sites
434 with hospitalised), and contained 69 WW-only sites not observed among
435 contemporaneously sequenced clinical genomes (Figure 2A). Consistent with this
436 pattern, mutation-set similarity was highest between hospitalised and non-hospitalised
437 clinical cases (Jaccard = 0.272), whereas overlap between WW and clinical mutations
438 was lower (Clinical vs WW Jaccard = 0.0946; HOSP vs WW = 0.1643; NonHOSP vs WW
439 = 0.1094) (Figure 2A,E). Notably, the overlap between hospitalised and WW mutation
440 sets (104 shared sites) was greater than expected given the dataset mutation universe
441 (Fisher's exact test OR = 1.77, $p = 1.82 \times 10^{-4}$; BH $q = 9.09 \times 10^{-4}$), indicating that WW
442 disproportionately captured mutations also present in the hospitalised group (Figure
443 S3).

444 In the hospital catchment dataset, hospitalised genomes harboured 281 mutations and
445 WW contained 86 (Figure 2B). We observed 62 shared mutation sites between
446 hospitalised cases and WW (shown as 124 counts in Figure 2B), yielding a slightly higher
447 overall overlap than in the metropolitan WWTP setting (HOSP vs WW Jaccard = 0.2033)
448 (Figure 2B,F). Most WW mutations were also observed in hospitalised cases (62/86,
449 72.1%), whereas the majority of hospitalised mutations were not recovered in WW
450 (219/281, 78.0%), and 24 sites were detected only in WW (Figure 2B). Across
451 catchments, clinical-WW overlap was higher in the hospital than in the metropolitan area
452 (Δ Jaccard = 0.1086), and this difference was supported by bootstrap resampling ($p <$
453 0.001).

454 Gene-level summaries showed that mutations were concentrated in ORF1ab and Spike,
455 with Spike contributing the largest mutation counts in both settings (WWTP metropolitan
456 area, total Spike mutations = 272; hospital = 64) (Figure 2C–D). Gene-level clinical-WW
457 overlap was strongest for structural genes, particularly M and Spike, and was higher in
458 the hospital catchment (hospital: M Jaccard = 0.50, Spike = 0.422) than in the
459 metropolitan WWTP dataset (WWTP metropolitan area: M = 0.229, Spike = 0.199)

460 (Figure 2E–F). In both datasets, Spike was significantly enriched for mutations shared
 461 between WW and clinical samples relative to clinical-only mutations (WW-TP
 462 metropolitan area: Fisher’s exact $p = 4.0 \times 10^{-6}$, BH $q = 8.8 \times 10^{-5}$; hospital: $p = 2.26 \times$
 463 10^{-4} , BH $q = 5.64 \times 10^{-3}$), consistent with preferential recovery of Spike variation in WW.
 464 Structural mapping further showed that shared and compartment-specific Spike
 465 mutations were distributed across the Spike surface (Figure 2G–H). We assessed if
 466 mutations were preferentially concentrated in certain Spike domains across groups
 467 (hospitalised, non-hospitalised and WW). In each dataset we first tested for global
 468 differences in domains using a χ^2 test, and then screened group–domain enrichments
 469 with one sided Fisher’s exact tests followed by Benjamini–Hochberg FDR correction. No
 470 domain enrichments remained significant after FDR correction (all $q \geq 0.05$), although
 471 we observed a trend in metropolitan area dataset, where we found enriched wastewater
 472 mutations in NTD domain (OR=2.93, $p=0.0077$, $q=0.0697$) compared to other groups.

473

474 **Figure 2. Shared SARS-CoV-2 mutations between clinical cases and wastewater samples in the**
 475 **WWTP Pinedo and hospital datasets. (A–B)** Venn diagrams summarising the overlap of detected
 476 mutations between hospitalised, non-hospitalised, and wastewater (WW) samples for the
 477 metropolitan dataset (A), and between hospitalised clinical cases and WW samples for the
 478 hospital dataset (B). **(C–D)** Number of shared mutations per gene across the same comparisons,
 479 shown for the Pinedo metropolitan dataset (C) and the hospital dataset (D). **(E–F)** Percentage of
 480 mutations shared between the groups of interest across all genes for the Pinedo metropolitan
 481 dataset (E) and the hospital dataset (F). **(G–H)** Structural mapping of shared and group-specific
 482 mutations onto the SARS-CoV-2 Spike protein. Mutations are displayed as spheres (“atoms”) on

483 the Spike structure; regions lacking sequencing coverage are not rendered as surfaces. A top
484 view of the trimer is shown on the left. Spike chains and surfaces are coloured by domain
485 annotation. Panels show results for the Pinedo metropolitan dataset (G) and the hospital dataset
486 (H).

487 Mutations associated to mild and severe cases

488 We investigated whether specific SARS-CoV-2 amino acid substitutions were
489 associated with hospitalisation (hospitalised vs non-hospitalised infections) across
490 three cohorts with increasing sample size: Comunitat Valenciana (n = 4,843), Spain (n
491 = 10,052), and a worldwide global cohort (n = 39,099) (Figure 3A–C). After restricting
492 to recurrent amino acid substitutions, we tested 143 variants in Valencia, 149 in Spain,
493 and 160 in the global cohort, applying Bonferroni correction ($\alpha \approx 3.50 \times 10^{-4}$, 3.36×10^{-4} ,
494 and 3.13×10^{-4} , respectively; Figure 3A–C). The number of Bonferroni-significant
495 associations increased with cohort size, from 5/143 (3.5%) in Valencia to 8/149 (5.4%)
496 in Spain and 35/160 (21.9%) in the global cohort. Significant signals were dominated by
497 variants associated with lower odds of hospitalisation ($\log_2(\text{OR}) < 0$): 5/5 protective in
498 Valencia, 5/8 protective in Spain, and 31/35 protective globally. Conversely, higher odds
499 for hospitalization (risk-associated variants) ($\log_2(\text{OR}) > 0$) were not detected at
500 Bonferroni significance in Valencia but were present in Spain (3/8) and in the global
501 cohort (4/35). The strongest signals by p-value were S:Q493E in Valencia ($\log_2(\text{OR}) =$
502 -0.94 ; $P = 9.14 \times 10^{-9}$), S:V83A in Spain ($\log_2(\text{OR}) = -0.50$; $P = 1.65 \times 10^{-25}$), and S:D796Y
503 in the global cohort ($\log_2(\text{OR}) = +0.24$; $P = 1.86 \times 10^{-70}$), with S:D796Y representing the
504 top risk association (Figure 3A–C). Bonferroni hits spanned multiple genes, with
505 significant variants distributed across 3 genes in Valencia, 2 genes in Spain, and 12
506 genes globally, consistent with substantially higher power in the largest cohort.

507 Cross-cohort reproducibility of stringent hits was limited (Figure 3D). Across all three
508 analyses, the union comprised 43 Bonferroni-significant variants, of which 30/43
509 (69.8%) were significant only in the global cohort, 4/43 (9.3%) only in Valencia, and
510 4/43 (9.3%) only in Spain. Overlap was restricted to 5/43 (11.6%) variants significant in
511 exactly two cohorts, with no variant significant in all three (Figure 3D). Pairwise overlap
512 tests supported this pattern: the global cohort and Valencia shared one hit
513 (nsp3:T1465I), which was not enriched over expectation (1.05 \times ; Fisher/hypergeometric
514 $P = 0.660$), whereas the global cohort and Spain shared four hits (S:D405N, S:G252V,
515 S:K417N, S:R408S) with a 2.52 \times enrichment over expectation ($P = 0.0497$). Valencia
516 and Spain shared zero Bonferroni hits ($P = 1.0$). Among variants significant in at least
517 two cohorts (n = 5), effect directions were largely concordant (4/5, 80%), comprising
518 three consistently protective variants and one consistently risk-associated variant,
519 while one variant showed discordant direction (one-sided binomial $P = 0.1875$) (Figure
520 3D). Beyond stringent hits, effect heterogeneity across cohorts was frequent: Cochran's
521 Q tests identified significant heterogeneity for 39/147 shared variants ($P < 0.05$),
522 including 4/5 replicated hits (S:G252V, nsp3:T1465I, S:K417N, S:R408S), whereas
523 S:D405N showed no evidence of heterogeneity (Q test $P = 0.527$) (Figure 3E).
524 Consistent with these results, concordance of effect sizes across all shared tested
525 variants was cohort-dependent. The global cohort showed a significant correlation with

526 Spain ($r = 0.327$, $P = 7.38 \times 10^{-5}$; bootstrap 95% CI 0.139–0.494), whereas correlations
527 were not significant for global vs Valencia ($r = 0.043$, $P = 0.617$) or Valencia vs Spain (r
528 $= 0.143$, $P = 0.0949$) (Figure 3E).

529 To complement single-variant testing, we fitted multivariable regularised interaction
530 models (glinetnet) and summarised the selected structure as interaction networks
531 (Figure 3F; Figure S4). In the worldwide cohort network shown in Supplemental Figure
532 S4D, the strongest interaction terms involved host covariates and viral substitutions, led
533 by nsp1:K47R \times sex (0.597), age \times sex (0.493), and age \times nsp1:K47R (0.454), followed
534 by nsp3:G489S \times sex (0.367) and nsp3:G1001S \times sex (0.173). In Spain (network in
535 Figure 3F), the largest interactions were predominantly between viral substitutions,
536 including S:G252V \times S:L455F (0.365) and S:K417N \times S:R408S (0.278). In both cohorts,
537 adding interaction terms substantially improved model fit compared with a main-
538 effects-only model, reducing deviance from 1.157 to 0.556 in the global cohort ($\Delta =$
539 0.601) and from 0.899 to 0.447 in Spain ($\Delta = 0.452$), and the inferred network structure
540 showed good bootstrap stability in the global cohort (21/21 nodes and 25/28 edges with
541 selection frequency ≥ 0.8) and moderate stability in Spain (85/152 nodes and 53/95
542 edges with selection frequency ≥ 0.8). These interaction networks therefore suggest
543 that, beyond additive effects, hospitalisation-associated signals can involve cohort-
544 specific dependencies between substitutions and host covariates, while the selected
545 edges should be interpreted as regularisation-derived statistical dependencies rather
546 than direct biological interactions.

570 Wastewater surveillance captures hospitalisation-associated 571 mutational signatures

572 To identify wastewater-detectable mutations with potential relevance to clinical
573 severity, we integrated three evidence layers: (i) detection in the two Valencia
574 wastewater catchments (I1, WW-Metropolitan; I2, WW-Hospital), (ii) main effects and
575 interactions selected by regularised network models trained on hospitalisation
576 outcomes in the Spain and global clinical cohorts ("Net Spain" and "Net global"), and
577 (iii) univariate hospitalisation association effect sizes ($\log_2(\text{OR})$) (Figure 4). This
578 prioritisation yielded 34 mutations, corresponding to 34/191 (17.8%) of wastewater-
579 detected mutations with support from at least one external layer (Figure 4A). In the
580 metropolitan dataset (I1), evidence-supported mutations were overwhelmingly shared
581 across hospitalised, non-hospitalised, and wastewater compartments ("All shared"),
582 and the distribution of network-supported mutations across epidemiological groups was
583 strongly non-random ($\chi^2 = 21.47$, $df = 3$, $P = 8.41 \times 10^{-5}$), consistent with severity-linked
584 signals being embedded within the broader circulating mutational background rather
585 than being exclusive to a single clinical outcome group (Figure 4A). Notably, only one
586 mutation classified as WW-only showed evidence in univariate association
587 (nsp10:E135K); all remaining prioritised mutations were "All shared", reinforcing that
588 most model-supported WW signals correspond to mutations also observed in clinical
589 genomes.

590 Spike accounted for 16/34 prioritised substitutions, mapping mainly to the NTD and RBD,
591 with fewer sites in SD1/SD2 and HR1 (Figure 4B). Among all Spike positions detected in
592 wastewater (51 sites), 13 were supported by the Net Spain model, 9 were supported by
593 univariate association, and 6 had evidence from both layers (Figure 4A–B). Directional
594 concordance between multivariable network inference and marginal association was
595 limited: only 2/6 (33%) of the dual-supported Spike substitutions showed concordant
596 directionality, namely S:T19I and S:E554K (protective across layers). In contrast, four
597 substitutions showed discordant directions between the multivariable network and
598 univariate association (S:V213E, S:G252V, S:R408S, S:K417N), consistent with context
599 dependence driven by co-occurring substitutions and lineage background (Figure 4A).
600 In particular, S:G252V showed a discordant pattern (non-hospitalised associated in Net
601 Spain but hospitalisation associated in univariate association), highlighting a plausible
602 context-dependent or confounded signal. Importantly, S:D405N (RBD) was the only
603 prioritised Spike substitution with a clear risk direction in univariate association
604 ($\log_2(\text{OR}) = +0.234$) and it was detected in the WW-hospital; I2) (Figure 4A–B).

605 Network structure within Spike further supported non-additive effects among
606 wastewater-detected sites (Figure 4C). The strongest Spike–Spike interaction
607 connected the RBD pair S:K417N–S:R408S ($|\text{coef}| = 0.278$), while NTD substitutions
608 formed an interaction module anchored by highly connected sites such as S:G252V and
609 S:S50L (for example, H146Q–G252V = 0.248; T19I–S50L = 0.229) (Figure 4C). Outside
610 Spike, several wastewater-detected mutations also mapped to severity models.
611 nsp1:K47R was particularly prominent, showing the largest main-effect magnitude in
612 Net Spain (coef = 0.350) and remaining selected in the Net global model (coef = 0.363),

613 with high interaction connectivity (Figure 4A). Notably, nsp1:K47R was “triple-positive”
 614 across layers but directionally discordant, being risk-associated in both network models
 615 while showing a protective direction in univariate association, underscoring that
 616 multivariable network models and univariate association capture complementary signals
 617 and can differ in direction when effects are conditional on genomic background or
 618 covariates (Figure 4A–C).

619
 620 **Figure 4. Multi-layer integration of wastewater-detected mutations linked to clinical severity. (A)**
 621 Summary table of mutations detected in wastewater with supporting evidence from multivariable
 622 network models (Spain and/or worldwide cohorts) and/or univariate hospitalisation association.
 623 Columns report: Gene (protein/ORF containing the substitution); Mutation (amino acid change;
 624 Spike entries include the structural domain when applicable); I1 and I2 (presence in the Valencia
 625 wastewater datasets: I1 = metropolitan; I2 = hospital; ✓ indicates detected); Group (I1) and Group
 626 (I2) (epidemiological category of the mutation within each dataset: WW only, HOSP+WW,
 627 NonHOSP+WW, or All shared); Net Spain and Net WW (direction of the main effect inferred by
 628 the regularised interaction network model in the Spain cohort and worldwide cohort,
 629 respectively; ↑ risk, ↓ protective, ↓ discordant/unstable, blank = not selected); Assoc Dir
 630 (direction from univariate association); Spain coef and WW coef (absolute magnitude of the
 631 main-effect coefficient in the fitted model); log₂(OR) (univariate effect size for
 632 hospitalisation; positive values indicate increased odds); # Sp part and # WW part (number of
 633 interaction partners for that mutation in the Spain and worldwide networks); and Top interaction
 634 partners (strongest interaction partners with their interaction coefficients). **(B)** Linear map of the
 635 Spike protein showing domain architecture (NTD, RBD, SD1, SD2, FP, HR1, CH, CD, HR2) and the
 636 positions of prioritised Spike substitutions. Marker colour indicates network direction (red, risk;
 637 blue, protective), marker shape indicates detection in I1, I2, or both datasets, and an orange
 638 outline marks substitutions that are also significant in univariate association. **(C)** Heatmap of
 639 absolute coefficients (|coef|) for prioritised Spike substitutions in the Spain clinical network
 640

641 model. Diagonal cells represent absolute main-effect coefficients, and off-diagonal cells
642 represent absolute pairwise interaction coefficients; darker colour indicates larger magnitude.

643 Discussion

644 Wastewater-based genomic surveillance is now widely recognised as a core
645 complement to patient-based sequencing because it can capture community
646 transmission signals independent of individual testing and can support public health
647 decision-making when clinical sampling becomes sparse^{15,34}. Early work showed that
648 wastewater RNA trajectories can track and even lead traditional indicators, including
649 hospital admissions, highlighting its value as a population-level sensor^{17,19}. Extending
650 wastewater monitoring from quantification to genomic characterisation has further
651 demonstrated that wastewater sequencing can detect variant turnover and “cryptic”
652 transmission that is not represented in clinical genomic datasets^{11,30,40–42}. In this context,
653 and aligned with WHO guidance that emphasises integrating wastewater and clinical
654 evidence streams, our study combined catchment-matched clinical and wastewater
655 sequencing in Valencia, Spain across two epidemiologically distinct datasets, a
656 metropolitan and a hospital, and used this framework to interpret wastewater-
657 detectable lineages and mutations in relation to clinical outcomes⁴³.

658 Wastewater performance in our data was clearly catchment dependent. The
659 metropolitan WW integrates a large and heterogeneous population, so its signal is
660 expected to be temporally smoothed by sewer transit, mixing, and spatially uneven
661 contributions, while the hospital collector reflects a more localised and clinically
662 enriched input. Technical realities of wastewater genomics further compound these
663 differences: wastewater contains fragmented RNA and mixtures of variants, and
664 sequencing and inference methods must operate under coverage dropouts and
665 haplotype ambiguity^{33,41}. At the mutation level, we observed that wastewater captured a
666 subset of the mutational space present in clinical genomes, with comparatively stronger
667 recovery of shared variation in structural genes, particularly Spike. This pattern is
668 biologically plausible because Spike is under strong immune selection, with repeated
669 convergent evolution at antigenic hotspots, especially within Omicron^{5,8,35}. It is also
670 methodologically plausible because wastewater sequencing is vulnerable to uneven
671 coverage and amplicon dropouts, so mutation detection becomes biased toward
672 consistently covered and highly selected regions, and Spike is often both well covered
673 and analytically prioritised^{33,41}. In our results, several prioritised sites mapped to
674 canonical antigenic regions, including RBD substitutions such as K417N (a well-
675 established antibody escape hotspot) and NTD substitutions such as G252V that fall
676 within the NTD supersite loop region targeted by neutralising antibodies^{44–46}. The
677 frequent discordance we observed between marginal (univariate) effect directions and
678 multivariable network-inferred directions for some Spike substitutions is consistent with
679 background dependence and epistasis, where the phenotypic effect of a substitution
680 depends on the co-occurring mutation set and host context rather than acting as an
681 independent additive marker.^{44,45,47} This interpretation is supported by experimental and
682 modelling work showing that Omicron immune escape is shaped by interacting

683 constellations of mutations and compensatory epistasis that preserves ACE2 affinity
684 while enabling escape.

685 A central contribution of the three-compartment design in the metropolitan dataset
686 (hospitalised, non-hospitalised, and wastewater) is that it makes explicit a category of
687 mutations observed only in wastewater. We interpret these wastewater-only sites as
688 potentially informative, but not in a simplistic “wastewater equals new variant” sense.
689 Instead, wastewater-only mutations can act as a proxy for transmission that is under-
690 ascertained in clinical datasets, including asymptomatic or mildly symptomatic
691 infections that do not seek testing or are not sequenced, as well as infections occurring
692 outside the clinical sampling frame^{11,15,34,40}. This is precisely the class of signal that
693 wastewater is expected to capture because it aggregates shedding from across the
694 infected population, independent of care-seeking behaviour. Multiple high-profile
695 studies have shown that wastewater sequencing can reveal cryptic SARS-CoV-2
696 diversity not represented in clinical databases, including lineages and spike haplotypes
697 detected repeatedly in wastewater but absent from clinical sampling^{11,31,32,42}. Importantly,
698 investigations tracing such cryptic signals have implicated persistent shedding from a
699 small number of individuals and extensive within-host evolution as one plausible
700 mechanism, illustrating that wastewater-only mutations can arise from under-sampled
701 human infections rather than from errors alone^{48,49}. At the same time, we emphasise that
702 wastewater-only mutations are not automatically interpretable as “asymptomatic”: they
703 may reflect low-prevalence lineages missed by sequencing, persistent infections,
704 stochastic detection in mixtures, or technical artefacts amplified by partial coverage and
705 read-depth constraints^{33,50}. Thus, in our framework, wastewater-only sites are best
706 treated as hypothesis-generating indicators of unobserved transmission that require
707 triangulation with temporal consistency, replicate detection, and external evidence
708 layers.

709 A key epidemiological observation is that, within the Omicron constellation circulating
710 during 2023 to early 2024, we did not detect clear lineage stratification by
711 hospitalisation status at the Nextclade clade resolution in the metropolitan dataset. This
712 is consistent with broader evidence that the largest changes in intrinsic severity were
713 associated with major variant transitions (for example, Delta to Omicron), whereas
714 within-Omicron severity differences are often modest and strongly shaped by time-
715 varying immunity, host risk structure, and healthcare context⁵¹. In our hospital catchment
716 window, clinical infections were dominated by JN.1 while wastewater frequently
717 detected BA.2.86 alongside JN.1, mirroring the rapid diversification within the BA.2.86
718 to JN.1 branch^{35,52}. Importantly, population-level analyses of the BA.2.86 and JN.1 period
719 have reported immune escape coupled with attenuated clinical severity compared with
720 contemporaneous XBB-derived lineages, reinforcing the interpretation that host and
721 immunity context dominate hospitalisation risk in this phase⁵. Together, these points
722 frame why strong, stable “virulence markers” are difficult to resolve at lineage level
723 within Omicron using hospitalisation as a binary endpoint.

724 Our severity association analyses and interaction networks reinforce why such
725 triangulation is essential. Across Valencia, Spain, and a large global cohort, the number

726 of Bonferroni-significant amino acid associations increased with sample size, but
727 stringent hits replicated poorly across cohorts and effect heterogeneity was
728 common^{39,53}. This is expected for a virus with strong linkage and rapid turnover,
729 analysed with a coarse phenotype such as hospitalisation⁵¹. Hospitalisation is shaped
730 by host factors and the evolving immunity landscape, which can confound viral
731 genotype associations even after adjusting for age, sex, and geography⁵⁴. The
732 dominance of host risk is supported by large-scale human genetics studies showing
733 that host genetic architecture and immune and inflammatory pathways are major
734 determinants of critical COVID-19 outcomes^{55,56}. In this setting, a viral mutation may
735 appear “protective” simply because it tags a lineage that circulated later in a more
736 immune population, or “risk-associated” because it tags a lineage concentrated in
737 vulnerable subpopulations or specific time windows^{51,54,57}. This makes cross-cohort
738 replication difficult and explains why multivariable regularised models, which can
739 partially absorb correlated structure and detect conditional dependencies, can disagree
740 in direction with marginal tests while still capturing clinically meaningful signal
741 structure⁵⁸.

742 The interaction networks provide a complementary lens to univariate testing by
743 explicitly allowing non-additive patterns that are plausible for Spike evolution under
744 immune pressure^{47,59,60}. In particular, convergent Omicron evolution has repeatedly
745 targeted RBD hotspots and NTD antigenic regions^{46,61}, and experimental work shows
746 that combinations of substitutions can jointly reshape antibody escape while
747 maintaining fitness, consistent with epistasis. Against that backdrop, network-identified
748 interaction structure among wastewater-detected Spike sites is not direct mechanistic
749 proof, but it is informative as a statistical signature of context dependence that can arise
750 from epistatic selection, lineage background, or shared immune-escape
751 trajectories^{47,59,60}. This is especially relevant for wastewater because short-read
752 mixtures and partial genome recovery limit haplotype reconstruction, so mutation co-
753 variation across time and samples may carry more reliable information than attempting
754 to assign full genomes from fragmented templates^{27,33,41,62}.

755 Two limitations deserve emphasis because they bound interpretation and motivate next
756 steps. First, wastewater genomic resolution in our study was constrained by incomplete
757 coverage, with approximately half of the genome covered on average in the retained
758 wastewater samples. In mixed and degraded templates, this directly reduces sensitivity
759 to mutations outside well-covered regions, biases spectra toward consistently captured
760 loci, and undermines haplotype reconstruction, all of which can affect both lineage calls
761 and mutation overlap metrics. Second, clinical severity was operationalised as a binary
762 hospitalisation endpoint^{27,33,41,62}. This phenotype collapses heterogeneous clinical
763 trajectories and is influenced by admission thresholds, comorbidity burden, vaccination
764 and prior infection history, and healthcare access, in addition to viral genetics. Host
765 genetic background adds further variance in risk, as demonstrated by critical illness
766 GWAS, but is not available in routine surveillance. These factors imply residual
767 confounding is likely even after covariate adjustment, and they argue for future analyses
768 using richer endpoints (ICU admission, oxygen requirement, death), immunological

769 history, and comorbidity indices, ideally integrated within sewershed-matched
770 designs^{51,54,57}.

771 Overall, our retrospective Valencia study supports a pragmatic interpretation of
772 wastewater genomics in the Omicron era^{15,33}. Wastewater sequencing can recover
773 dominant variant waves and enrich for clinically relevant mutation classes (especially
774 Spike), but the degree of concordance, timeliness, and interpretability depends strongly
775 on sewershed context and achievable genomic resolution¹¹. At the same time, the three-
776 compartment design highlights a distinct added value of wastewater: the appearance
777 of wastewater-only mutations and lineages that are consistent with integration of
778 shedding from under-ascertained infections. High-impact studies have repeatedly
779 documented cryptic wastewater diversity not seen clinically and have provided
780 evidence that such signals can originate from rare, persistent, or otherwise unsampled
781 human infections. In that sense, wastewater-only sites in our dataset can be interpreted
782 as a proxy for missingness in clinical surveillance, plausibly including asymptomatic
783 transmission, but only when combined with careful quality control, temporal
784 consistency checks, and external evidence layers. This motivates a multi-layer
785 framework, aligned with recent methodological guidance and ongoing tool
786 development, where wastewater mutation calls are not treated as definitive on their own
787 but are prioritised and interpreted using complementary clinical association evidence
788 and robust modelling of co-variation under mixture and low-coverage constraints^{33,41,63}.

789 Disclosure statement

790 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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810 review & editing; **APC:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review &
811 editing; **MTP:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing;
812 **CGC:** Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing; **IC:**
813 Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing; **GS:** Methodology,
814 Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing; **FGC:** Funding
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